

**Organizational Culture and a Safety-Conscious Work Environment: The
Mediating Role of Employee Communication Satisfaction**

Silla, I., Navajas, J., & Koves, K. (2017). Organizational Culture and a Safety-Conscious Work Environment: The Mediating Role of Employee Communication Satisfaction. *Journal of Safety Research*, 61, 121–127.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jsr.2017.02.005>

Abstract

Problem: A safety-conscious work environment allows high-reliability organizations to be proactive regarding safety and enables employees to feel free to report any concern without fear of retaliation. Currently, research on the antecedents to safety-conscious work environments is scarce.

Method: Structural equation modeling was applied to test the mediating role of employee communication satisfaction in the relationship between constructive culture and a safety-conscious work environment in several nuclear power plants.

Results: Employee communication satisfaction partially mediated the positive relationships between a constructive culture and a safety-conscious work environment.

Conclusions: Constructive cultures in which cooperation, supportive relationships, individual growth and high performance are encouraged facilitate the establishment of a safety-conscious work environment. This influence is partially explained by increased employee communication satisfaction.

Practical Application: Constructive cultures should be encouraged within organizations. In addition, managers should promote communication policies and practices that support a safety-conscious work environment.

Keywords: High Reliability Organizations, Nuclear Power Plants, Constructive Culture, Structural Equation Modeling (SEM)

1. INTRODUCTION

In high-reliability organizations (HROs), a safety-conscious work environment (SCWE) may help prevent catastrophic accidents that can have serious human, economic, and environmental consequences (e.g., INPO -Institute of Nuclear Power Operations-, 2013; NEI -Nuclear Energy Institute-, 2003). Many types of organizations can be HROs, including chemical plants, aircraft companies, and nuclear power plants, among others.

Accidents are extremely rare in HROs. Nonetheless, failures in system components (e.g., people, equipment, procedures) can interact in unpredictable ways (Perrow, 1984). In addition, because there is high interdependence among system components, failures may cascade into even greater problems before operators can understand the situation (Perrow, 1984). Subsequently, HROs (i.e., nuclear power plants) continuously monitor safety and attempt to anticipate potential problems (Morrow, Koves, & Barnes, 2014).

Therefore, research on SCWEs and their antecedents has practical implications that are relevant for HRO safety. A SCWE is common in those organizations in which employees feel free to raise any concerns to their managers, which managers can use to obtain a complete picture of the organizational state of operations and to identify “weak cases” or “early warning signs” of safety degradation (e.g., Pidgeon, 1997).

This study, which was conducted in several nuclear power plants, aims to examine the relationship between constructive culture and SCWEs and to assess the mediating role of employee satisfaction with organizational communication in this relationship.

1.1. *Constructive culture and a SCWE*

Previous research suggests that organizational culture is vital for safety in HROs (e.g., the post-accident investigation into the Challenger disaster) (Vaughan, 2009). Nonetheless, the myriad conceptualizations of organizational culture (e.g., Reason, 1997; Turner & Pidgeon, 1997) have prevented the accumulation of knowledge (e.g., Sackmann, 2011). This study attempts to counteract this difficulty by detailing the conceptualization of organizational culture we have adopted.

Organizational culture has been alternatively defined as “*the way we do things around here*” (Deal & Kennedy, 1982) or as shared symbols, rituals, beliefs, stories, ideologies, values, practices, knowledge, or artifacts (Smircich, 1983), among other definitions. By focusing on constructive culture, this study refers to thinking and behavioral norms. In other words, it addresses the “unwritten rules” that are required to “fit in” and “survive” within an organization (Cooke & Szumal, 2000). These norms refer to the approaches applied to address work and to interact with others.

Constructive cultures encourage members to interact with others and to approach tasks with the aim of meeting their own higher order satisfaction needs (Cooke & Lafferty, 2003). As such, these organizations promote cooperation, supportive relationships among work colleagues, high-level performance, and individual growth (Cooke & Rousseau, 1988; Cooke & Szumal, 2000).

Constructive cultures balance both people and task orientation and support the attainment of higher order satisfaction needs (Denison et al., 2014). Both aspects are critical for conceptualizing organizational culture (for a literature review, see Detert, Schroeder, & Mauriel, 2000; and Xenicou & Furnham, 1996), and both rest on sound theoretical foundations. The distinction between people orientation (e.g., concern about employees’ satisfaction and overall well-being) and task orientation (e.g.,

accomplishments of specific goals and execution of the applicable steps to be followed) is well established in the field of organizational culture (e.g., Denison et al., 2014) and leadership (Balthazard & Cooke, 2004; Cooke & Szumal, 1993). Additionally, the concept of higher order satisfaction needs (e.g., self-esteem, achievement, and creativity) was first introduced by Maslow (1954) in his hierarchical theory of motivation. This theoretical approach is well-known in the organizational culture literature (e.g., Denison, Nieminen, & Kotrba, 2014; Ostroff, Kinicki, & Tamkins, 2003; Xenicou & Furnham, 1996).

The notion of constructive culture has been applied in HROs, including nuclear power plants (e.g., García-Herrero, Mariscal, Gutiérrez, & Toca-Otero, 2013; Klein, Bigley, & Roberts, 1995), and in other organizational contexts (e.g., Pool, 2000; Kwantes & Boglarsky, 2004). Moreover, there is extensive research supporting the reliability and validity of the constructive culture construct (e.g., Denison et al., 2014; Xenikou & Furnham, 1996), which is necessary to discriminate among various types of organizations. A comparative study revealed that constructive culture varied among HROs and “conventional” organizations and among different types of HROs (Klein et al., 1995).

Finally, it is notable that an examination of safety culture is outside the scope of this study. Most theoretical developments regarding safety culture derive from a more generalized notion of organizational culture (Glendon & Stanton, 2000) and respond to “*analytical or practical reasons to narrow the concept and thus make it more tangible*” (Guldenmund, 2000; p. 223). For instance, according to Pidgeon (1991), safety culture refers to “*norms and rules for handling hazards, attitudes toward safety, and reflexivity on safety practice*” (p.135). Constructive culture does not refer to safety thinking and behavioral norms, and its theoretical foundations are sufficiently meaningful and broad

to establish parallels with alternative models of organizational culture (Detert et al., 2000; Xenicou & Furnham, 1996). In so doing, this approach allows for an accumulation of knowledge in the field of organizational culture (Denison et al., 2014).

This study aims to examine the relationship between constructive culture and the SCWE. The SCWE, which has captured increased practitioner attention in the nuclear sector (INPO, 2013; NRC -Nuclear Regulatory Commission-, 2011), has been considered as a relevant feature of safety culture by some international organizations (INPO, 2013). However, in the field of social sciences, several authors recommend to avoid the use of safety culture as an “umbrella term” (Guldenmund, 2010; p. 1466) and acknowledge its risks. In the words of Guldenmund (2010), safety culture is a “fuzzy” concept, “this fuzziness is both its strength and its weakness” (Guldenmund, 2010; p. 1466).

The SCWE implies that “... *personnel feel free to raise safety concerns without fear of retaliation, intimidation, harassment, or discrimination*” (INPO, 2013; p. 6). NEI (2003) extends the scope of a SCWE to non-safety-related concerns and establishes that SCWE policies should allow employees the freedom to express both safety-related and non-safety-related concerns to management without fear of reprisal. The current study also focuses on employee concerns that are not necessarily related to safety as a way to determine whether employees are proactive. It is important to consider that the distinction between safety- and non-safety-related concerns is not always obvious. For instance, the event that occurred in 2002 at Davis-Besse nuclear power plant illustrates how discrepancies that did not seem significant in terms of safety (rust particles in containment air filters) were a sign of safety degradation (Perin, 2005). Accordingly, Weick and Sutcliffe (2007) emphasize the need to note small discrepancies whenever they may occur and to address failures in early stages.

Constructive culture is expected to facilitate the establishment of a SCWE for several reasons. Constructive cultures fulfill individual higher order satisfaction needs. Subsequently, based on the social exchange norm of reciprocity (Blau, 1964), employees may feel obligated to support a SCWE (Blau, 1964). Constructive cultures also promote supportive relationships, which allow individuals to feel secure when raising concerns to their managers instead of glossing over or hiding them. Having supportive relationships might reduce interpersonal risks when raising concerns, such that raising concerns is not perceived as an act of disloyalty or a willingness to interfere in the work of co-workers, for example (Navajas, Silla, & Guldenmund, 2014).

Moreover, empirical research has shown that constructive culture benefits organizational functioning (see Cooke & Szumal, 2000 for an integrative review), employee commitment (Haley, 1998; Klein et al., 1995; Roberts, Rousseau, & La Porte, 1994), job satisfaction (Balthazard, Cooke, & Potter, 2006; Cooke & Szumal, 2000; Stebbins, 2008), role clarity (Balthazard et al., 2006; Pool, 2000), cooperation (Murphy, Cooke, & Lopez, 2013), quality of organizational communication (Balthazard et al., 2006), and organizational products/service quality (Balthazard et al., 2006; Murphy et al., 2013).

Although previous research supports the benefits of constructive culture regarding safety (e.g., García-Herrero et al., 2013; Rousseau, 1989), empirical evidence of these benefits remains scarce. García-Herrero et al. (2013) found constructive culture to be positively associated with safety culture. By contrast, Haley (1998) found a positive relationship between constructive culture and reported medication errors and patient falls, which could be explained by the transparency associated with constructive culture. This transparency might account for the increased number of reported incidents and suggests that fewer reported incidents in some organizations may not necessarily

reflect the number of incidents actually occurring. Therefore, the following hypothesis was formulated:

Hypothesis 1. Constructive culture will be positively associated with a SCWE.

1.1. The mediating role of employee satisfaction with organizational communication

This study attempts to more thoroughly evaluate the relationship between constructive culture and a SCWE. This evaluation is achieved by examining the mediating role of employee satisfaction with organizational communication, which is defined as “*the collective and interactive process of generating and interpreting messages*” (Stohl, 1995; p. 4).

Several arguments support the mediating role of satisfaction with organizational communication. First, organizational culture is expected to influence organizational communication by enabling and constraining it (Bisel, Messermith, & Keyton, 2010). Thus, in some sense, organizational culture sets the basis for communication (de Cock, de Witte, & van Nieuwkerke, 1998; Langan-Fox, 2001). The implementation of communication policies and practices will fail if they are not aligned with organizational culture (Xie, Helfert, Lugmayr, Heimgärtner, & Holzinger, 2013). With respect to the connection between constructive culture and communication, Murphy et al. (2013) suggest that constructive culture would increase communication quality and individual interaction. Similarly, Balthazard et al. (2006) provide empirical evidence regarding the positive relationship between constructive culture and communication quality.

Second, employee satisfaction with organizational communication is expected to enhance a stronger SCWE. Organizational communication contributes to employee performance (Agarwal, 2010). For instance, it keeps members informed about ongoing operations and helps them identify “early warnings” of safety degradation (Weick &

Sutcliffe, 2007). In addition, well-informed employees may feel legitimized and confident enough to raise any type of concern to their superiors. Finally, communication accomplishes an educational function (Cigularov, Chen, & Rosecrance, 2010) that may support SCWE, instill caution and discourage complacency by providing relevant information, such as information about near misses, system status, etc. (Reason, 1997).

In summary, constructive culture is expected to benefit both organizational communication and SCWEs. Additionally, satisfying organizational communication can promote a SCWE. Based on the arguments discussed above, the following hypothesis was formulated:

Hypothesis 2. Employee communication satisfaction will partially mediate the positive relationship between constructive culture and a SCWE.

2. METHOD

2.1. Participants and procedure

This study was framed in a research project conducted in several nuclear power plants. Researchers informed all participants about the aims of the study during group sessions, emphasizing the confidential nature of the study and voluntary participation. Questionnaires were completed during work hours.

The sample consisted of 1,481 employees. The average response rate across the different nuclear power plants was 69.16% (ranging from 62% to 89%). Approximately 7.08% of the participants were managers and department heads, and 92.92% held lower-level job positions. Most employees were university graduates (university degree: 47.65%; high school graduates: 14.61%; vocational training: 29.81%; elementary school: 7.93%). Regarding organizational tenure, 65.44% of the employees had at least 20 years experience with their respective organization.

Participants stem from three companies geographically distributed across eight different locations which run five different nuclear power plants. Box's M statistic and Levene test for equality of variances were conducted to assess whether data pertaining to the three different companies can be combined and analyzed together. All the variables examined in the hypothesized model were considered. Box's M statistic tests homogeneity of covariance matrices across the three examined companies. The null hypothesis of equal covariance matrices is rejected when $p \leq .005$ (Huberty & Petoskey, 2000) or $.001$ (Tabachnick & Fidell, 2007). Results showed the null hypothesis could not be rejected: $M=63.223$, $p=.02$. Seemingly, Levene test supported homogeneity of variances across the three companies. The only exception was one out of the four dimensions of constructive culture: Self-actualizing ($F=3.17$, $p=.04$). All together, findings suggested that data gathered from the three different companies can be combined and analyzed together.

In addition, one-way MANOVA was carried out to detect whether the three companies differ along the combination of variables examined in the hypothesized model (constructive culture dimensions, employee communication satisfaction, and safety-conscious work environment). Findings showed statistically significant differences: $F(12, 2806) = 11.07$, $p < .001$; Wilk's $\Lambda = 0.91$, partial $\eta^2 = .04$. In addition, when one-way ANOVA was conducted on each dependent variable, statistically significant differences emerged on achievement ($F(2, 1408) = 6.54$; $p < .01$; $\eta^2 = .01$), affiliative ($F(2, 1408) = 3.62$; $p = .03$; $\eta^2 = .005$), employee communication satisfaction ($F(2, 1408) = 25.80$; $p < .01$; $\eta^2 = .03$), and safety-conscious work environment ($F(2, 1408) = 9.40$; $p < .01$; $\eta^2 = .01$). Differences in Humanistic-Encouraging and Self-actualizing were statistically non-significant ($p \geq .05$). Based on

these findings, company was included in the hypothesized model as control variable (See data analysis).

2.2. Measures

The measures used in this study are described hereafter. Scale reliability and the factorial structure are presented in the “Results” section.

Constructive culture. The Organizational Culture Inventory®¹ developed by Cooke and Lafferty (2003) was used to measure constructive culture. A five-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (“1. Not at all”) to 5 (“5. To a very great extent”) was used. Constructive culture was measured using the following four subscales (Cronbach’s alpha: .96): Humanistic-Encouraging, Affiliative, Achievement, and Self-actualizing (Cooke & Szumal, 2000; p. 149). Ten items were used to measure *Humanistic-Encouraging* culture (Cronbach’s alpha: .93), which represents organizations in which “[m]embers are expected to be supportive, constructive, and open to influence in their dealings with one another”. The *affiliative* culture scale (Cronbach’s alpha: .92) consisted of ten items and features organizations in which “[m]embers are expected to be friendly, cooperative, and sensitive to the satisfaction of their work group”. The *achievement* culture (Cronbach’s alpha: .86), was assessed with a ten-item scale and determines whether “[m]embers are expected to set challenging but realistic goals, establish plans to reach those goals, and pursue them with enthusiasm”. The *self-actualizing* culture scale (Cronbach’s alpha: .83) consisted of ten items and represents organizations in which “[m]embers are expected to enjoy their work, develop themselves, and take on new and interesting tasks”.

¹ Organizational Culture Inventory® is a registered trademark of Human Synergistics International, Plymouth, MI, USA; Copyright 1973-2006 by Human Synergistics International. Used by permission.

Employee communication satisfaction was assessed using a single-item measure, with a response scale ranging from 1 (low satisfaction) to 7 (high satisfaction). This item reads as follows “*Choose the side that best describes your opinion of communications at your organization, taking into consideration aspects such as the information load, interaction with your immediate boss and others, and the accuracy of available information, among others.*”

The *SCWE* was measured using four items with a response scale ranging from 1 (“1. *Completely agree*”) to 7 (“7. *Completely disagree*”) (S. Haber, personal communication, September 2006). This scale, which was elaborated following NEI (2003) and NRC (2005) guidelines on SCWEs, assesses the extent to which employees feel free to raise concerns and challenge decisions. In addition, the scale measures the level of employee confidence that management will willingly listen to their concerns, address them constructively and will not engage in retaliation; a sample item is “*Management does not tolerate retaliation of any kind for raising concerns*”. Cronbach’s alpha was .85.

2.3.Data analysis

Descriptive statistics, the correlation matrix between variables, and alpha coefficients were computed (Table 1). Additionally, confirmatory factor analyses (CFAs) were performed to examine the validity of the scales presented above. Finally, structural equation modeling (SEM) was used to test the hypotheses.

The measurement model included the constructive culture and SCWE items. A maximum likelihood method (ML) was used to estimate model parameters, and a covariance matrix served as analysis input. With respect to the constructive culture scale, the measurement model consisted of one second-order factor (constructive culture) and four first-order factors: humanistic-encouraging, affiliative, achievement,

and self-actualizing. Several studies (e.g., Denison et al., 2014; Xenikou & Furnham, 1996) provide empirical evidence that support the notion that conceptualizing constructive culture as a higher order factor is reliable and valid. In addition, Denison et al. (2014) argue that it is possible to conceptually connect to other theoretical organizational culture models through higher order factors by helping to overcome the difficulty of accumulating empirical evidence caused by diverse coexisting models. A single-factor model was tested for the SCWE scale.

Using structural equation modeling (SEM), three competing models were examined for purposes of testing the hypothesized model (Figure 1). These models combined CFA and path analysis. To reduce the number of parameters to be estimated, the humanistic-encouraging, affiliative, achievement, and self-actualizing subscales served as indicators of constructive culture. Maximum likelihood (ML) methods were used to estimate model parameters, and a covariance matrix was employed for analysis input. Finally, in order to avoid potential confounding effects, Company was introduced as a control variable (See one-way MANOVA and ANOVA results in the section “2.1. Participants and procedure”). Company is a categorical variable with three levels, thus, two dummy variables ($k-1$) were introduced as control variables (Company I and Company II).

Our hypothesized partial mediation model predicts that a constructive culture will be positively associated with a SCWE (Hypothesis 1) and that employee communication satisfaction will mediate this relationship (Hypothesis 2). This partial mediation model was compared with two competing models: a full mediation model and a direct effects model. The full mediation model tests whether the effect of constructive culture on the SCWE is fully exerted indirectly through the mediator. The

direct effects model (non-mediated model) tests the influence of constructive culture and employee communication satisfaction on the SCWE.

To assess model fit, we examined the standardized root mean residual (SRMR), root mean square of approximation (RMSEA) and comparative fit index (CFI) (Kline, 2005). For SRMR and RMSEA, lower values indicate a better fit. Upper limits of .08 for SRMR and RMSEA (RMSEA \leq .05= close fit; .05<RMSEA \leq .08 = reasonable fit) have been recognized as acceptable. By contrast, higher CFI values indicate a better fit: a value \geq 0.90 indicates a good fit. Additionally, the χ^2 fit statistics of the various models were statistically compared using $\Delta \chi^2_{(df1-df2)} = \chi^2_{(df1)} - \chi^2_{(df2)}$ (Mueller & Hancock, 2008).

3. RESULTS

Descriptive statistics, alpha coefficients, and correlations for all measures are presented in Table 1. Pearson correlations revealed positive relations among constructive culture, employee communication satisfaction and a SCWE (p<.01).

Table 1.

Descriptive statistics, alpha coefficients and correlations

Variable	M	SD	1	2	3	4	5
1. Company I (CI)	--	--	--	--			
2. Company II (CII)	--	--	--	--			
3. Constructive culture	3.49	.63	.02	-.07**	(.96)		
4. Employee communication satisfaction	4.63	1.39	-.01	-.18**	.44**	--	
5. Safety-Conscious Work Environment (SCWE)	4.41	1.52	-.11**	.07*	.31**	.40**	(.85)

Note: *p<.05 and **p<.01. Reliabilities (coefficient alpha) are given in parentheses.

The measurement model consisting of constructive culture (second-order factor model) and SCWE (single-factor model) showed an acceptable fit to the data (SRMR=.05; RMSEA=.066; CFI=.85). SRMR and RMSEA values were satisfactory. Additionally, RMSEA with a 90% CI (.065, .068) was also acceptable. However, CFI was below the minimum requirements.

To test our hypotheses, the partial mediation model was tested (See Figure 1). In addition, the fit of this model was compared with the fit of each of the other two models: full mediation and direct effects (Table 2). The partial mediation model showed an acceptable fit to the data ($\chi^2=247.762$, $df=39$, $p<.01$; SRMR=.03; RMSEA=.06; CFI=.97), as did the full mediation model ($\chi^2=278.956$, $df=40$, $p<.01$; SRMR=.05; RMSEA=.07; CFI=.97). However, the chi-square difference test showed that the partial mediation model was a significantly better fit than the full mediation model: χ^2 difference ($df=1$)=31.19, $p<.01$. With respect to the direct effects model (non-mediated model), the goodness of fit indexes displayed a poor fit ($\chi^2=535.430$, $df=40$, $p<.01$; SRMR=.11; RMSEA=.09; CFI=.94).

The findings indicated that the preferred model is the partial mediation model. Additionally, all the estimated parameters were statistically significant ($p<.05$) and supported the hypotheses (Figure 1). Constructive culture exerted a positive direct effect on SCWE (hypothesis 1) and employee communication satisfaction. Constructive culture effects on SCWE were partially mediated by employee communication satisfaction, with the standardized indirect effect estimated at .16 ($p<.01$) (hypothesis 2). Finally, the R^2 for the variance explained in SCWE was .23. In conclusion, the hypotheses described above were fully supported.

Table 2. Goodness of fit indicators of the three competing models

	χ^2	<i>Df</i>	SRMR	RMSEA	90% CI for RMSEA	CFI
1. Partial mediation	247.762	39	.03	.06	.05-.07	.97
2. Full mediation	278.956	40	.05	.07	.06-.07	.97
3. Direct effects	535.430	40	.11	.09	.09-.10	.94

Figure 1. Structural equation modeling results: Partial mediation model. * $p < .05$; ** $p < .01$.

4. DISCUSSION

The purpose of this study was to examine the mediating role of employee communication satisfaction in the relationship between constructive culture and a SCWE. Consistent with hypothesis 1, constructive culture was accompanied by a more SCWE. Additionally, employee communication satisfaction partially mediated this relationship (Hypothesis 2), and the findings supported the formulated hypotheses. Regarding control variables, findings showed that company was a significant predictor of communication satisfaction and a SCWE. Finally, unreported analyses provided additional support to Hypothesis 2 by means of showing that the indirect effect of employee communication satisfaction was equal across companies. In particular, multiple group comparisons using SEM were conducted, and the indirect effect was constrained to be equal in the three companies. The model showed an acceptable fit to the data ($\chi^2=325.887$, $df=101$, $p<.01$; SRMR=.05; RMSEA=.069; CFI=.971).

These findings are consistent with previous research supporting constructive culture benefits for safety culture (e.g., García-Herrero et al, 2013) and for relevant individual and organizational outcomes (e.g., Balthazard & Cooke, 2004; Cooke & Szumal, 2000). Moreover, the results are also consistent with several theoretical arguments that support the mediating role of employee communication satisfaction. Several authors have noted the influence of organizational culture on communication (e.g., Langan-Fox, 2001; Xie et al., 2013) and the positive association between constructive culture and communication quality (Balthazard et al., 2006; Murphy et al., 2013). Additionally, the previous literature supports the relationship between communication and a SCWE. In particular, some authors have focused on communication, as it positively impacts performance (Agarwal, 2010) and has an

educational function (Cigularov et al., 2010), which may promote a SCWE by encouraging caution.

This study has several theoretical implications. It provides evidence of the applicability of constructive culture theoretical foundations in HROs. Most research on the benefits of constructive culture has been conducted in “conventional organizations” and thus cannot be easily transferred to HROs (Waller & Roberts, 2003), which are known for unique characteristics that must be considered when developing predictive theoretical models (e.g., Johns, 2006). It appears that the knowledge developed in HROs cannot apply directly to “conventional organizations” because practices such as on-the-job training, peer-checks, or emergency drills (Sagan, 1993) may not be cost-effective in “conventional organizations”.

Our findings suggest that organizational cultures supporting higher order satisfaction needs and balancing out people and task orientation (which is the case with constructive culture) would benefit HROs. Similarly, Rousseau (1989) postulated that humanistic and satisfaction-oriented values are necessary in HROs during periods of crisis that require decentralized decision making.

By contrast to these arguments, high reliability and normal accident theorists postulate the need for a “strong” organizational culture during normal operations (Sagan, 1993). These authors argue that a strong organizational culture “*in the form of intense socialization [and] strict discipline (...) can encourage safety with hazardous technologies*” (Sagan, 1993; p. 252-253). A “strong” organizational culture depends on high control and centralization according to high reliability theorists, who argue that this type of organization ensures that front-line employees will act predictably and support safety to achieve hierarchical approval. However, high reliability theorists also acknowledge the potential side effects of fostering a “strong” organizational culture. For

instance, it may encourage excessive conformity and institutional loyalty and instill a fear of retaliation when mistakes are articulated (Sagan, 1993). All these aspects would be counterproductive for a SCWE. Additionally, a “strong” culture would not be helpful when employees face unexpected circumstances. This study encourages further research to address the influence of constructive culture on other safety related outcomes to shed additional light on this debate.

This study contributes to the development of an integrative theoretical model on SCWEs and on their antecedents and intervening variables. In particular, this study suggests that constructive cultures support a SCWE in a relationship partially mediated by employee communication satisfaction. Many practitioners acknowledge the relevance of a SCWE (INPO, 2013; NRC, 2011) and note some antecedents. Nonetheless, research in this field of social science remains scarce.

Finally, this study suggests that social exchange theory may illuminate the understanding of SCWE (Blau, 1964) antecedents in HROs. Constructive cultures may help employees feel that their organization values their contributions and encourages them to feel obligated to support a SCWE (Blau, 1964).

These findings have relevant practical implications and suggest that organizational policies that support a constructive culture should be encouraged. Szumal (2009) postulated that shaping an environment that is conducive to learning and development and viewing members as an important source of ideas promotes a constructive culture. Additionally, communication policies supporting a SCWE should be implemented. For instance, effective communication channels help inform employees regarding the big picture of the organization such that they can identify signs of safety degradation (e.g., Roberts & Bea, 2001). Additionally, practices such as good

two-way communication channels and a reward system that reinforces the actions of employees who raise concerns may further strengthen a SCWE.

Research on SCWE antecedents also has some practical implications for our society. A HRO system failure may lead to substantial human, economic, and environmental costs. A SCWE enables the organization to identify signs of safety degradation before an accident occurs. This proactive approach is crucial in HROs in which multiple small independent failures may lead to safety degradation without any of these failures necessarily being documented in accident statistics (HSE -Health and Safety Executive-, 2011) until it is too late.

This study also has multiple limitations. Due to its cross-sectional nature, causal relationships cannot be assumed. Despite several theoretical arguments suggesting that organizational culture influences communication, this relationship might be reversed or reciprocal. Organizational culture enables and constrains communication (Bisel et al., 2010). However, cultures are created, sustained, transmitted, and changed through communication and social interaction (Schall, 1983). In any case, it may be argued that social and cultural rules are relatively stable, although they might evolve through social interaction (Conrad & Haynes, 2001). An additional limitation is that this study was based on self-reported data. Future studies should incorporate objective SCWE measurements (e.g., number of reported “near incidents”). Finally, employee communication satisfaction was measured through a single-item measure. However, in some instances such as overall job satisfaction single-item measures has been considered robust (Nagy, 2002; Wanous, Reichers, & Hudy, 1997). These authors argue that, first; single-item measures are much more efficient. Second, single-item measures may be more convenient than summing up facet scales which may neglect relevant job

features for a given employee. Third, they provide empirical evidence suggesting that overall job satisfaction single-item measures are acceptable for measurement purposes.

With respect to future research, social scientists should address the theoretical development and empirical validity of the SCWE construct. Despite international organizations (INPO, 2013; NRC, 2011) have emphasized its relevance in high reliability organizations based on their expert judgment, to date, research in the field of social science is scarce. In addition, practitioners refer to the SCWE as a relevant attribute of safety culture. These pragmatic approaches (experience-based) makes it difficult to prevent safety culture to become a fuzzy concept. Notice that pragmatic approaches include under the term “safety culture”: *“the structure and processes of an organization, which, because of their dynamic interplay, will subsequently influence the culture and, in due course, behavior and performance”* of an organization (Guldenmund, 2010; p. 1470). Along these lines, several researchers acknowledge that it is common to use the concept of safety culture as an “umbrella” term *“to explain everything relating to safety failures that cannot be explained in another way”* (Guldenmund, 2010, p. 1466).

Future research should also identify other potential intervening factors in the relationship between organizational culture and SCWE. For instance, a potential moderating factor might be the type of concern to be raised. Reporting an individual’s potential error may have negative consequences that might discourage employees from raising concerns (Dekker, 2007), even when a constructive culture is promoted.

Finally, future studies should test the generalizability of the results with “conventional” organizations. Some studies have documented distinctive characteristics of HROs (Roberts, 1990), but less is known about their similarities with “conventional” organizations. Qualitative studies may help further explain this difference. Such an

investigation would not justify a generalization of our findings, but it might be insightful to create new knowledge (e.g., Tamuz & Harrison, 2006; Vogus & Welbourne, 2003; Waller & Roberts, 2003). For instance, any “conventional” organization pursuing production process reliability (e.g., organizations manufacturing jet engines) may benefit from research conducted in HROs.

Along these lines, future research should contribute to develop more comprehensive models on organizational culture that addresses socio-cultural, organizational, and individual variables (e. g., Erez & Gati, 2004; Fischer, Ferreira, Assmar, Redford, & Harb 2005; Rousseau, 1985). For instance, Ostroff, Kinicki, & Tamkins (2003) emphasize the influence of national culture, industry and business environment, and organizational vision and strategy on individuals’ perception of organizational culture. Cross-level research addressing the effects of higher-level characteristics on lower-level processes would shed light into these and other research questions such as how strongly individuals perceptions of organizational culture are influenced by company, organizational branch or work group.

5. CONCLUSION

The concept of a SCWE is gaining increased attention among practitioners because it allows organizations to anticipate potential problems and prevent accidents in HROs (INPO, 2013; NEI, 2003; NRC, 2011). Additionally, some international organizations have developed guidelines regarding how to maintain and encourage a SCWE (INPO, 2013; NEI, 2003; NRC, 2011). Nonetheless, in the field of social sciences, research on the antecedents of SCWEs is scarce.

This study fills this research gap by contributing to evidence-based safety management. The findings suggest that organizational cultures that support the attainment of higher order satisfaction needs and that balance task and people

orientation (which is the case for constructive culture) support a SCWE. Additionally, a constructive culture also influences a SCWE by increasing employee communication satisfaction.

The practical implications of these results are relevant for human society because accidents in HROs can have catastrophic consequences in terms of human, environmental and economic costs. Finally, this study encourages future research to examine the influence of constructive culture on other safety-related outcomes.

REFERENCES

- Agarwal, O. P., 2010. *Effective Communication*. Mumbai: Himalaya Publishing House
- Balthazard, P. A., & Cooke, R. A. (2004). Organizational culture and knowledge management success: assessing the behavior-performance continuum. *IEEE proceedings of the 37th Annual Hawaii International Conference on System Science*. Hawaii: IEEE Xplore.
- Balthazard, P. A., Cooke, R. A., & Potter, R. E. (2006). Dysfunctional culture, dysfunctional organization: Capturing the behavioral norms that form organizational culture and drive performance. *Journal of Managerial Psychology*, 21 (8), 709-732.
- Bisel, R. S., Messersmith, A. S., & Keyton, J. (2010). Understanding organizational culture and communication through a gyroscope metaphor. *Journal of Management Education*, 34 (3), 342-366.
- Blau, P. M. (1964). *Exchange and Power in Social Life*. New York, NY: John Wiley & Sons, Inc.
- Cigularov, K. P., Chen, P. Y., & Rosecrance, J. (2010). The effects of error management climate and safety communication on safety: A multi-level study. *Accident Analysis & Prevention*, 42 (5), 1498-1506.
- Conrad, C., & Haynes, J. (2001). Development of key constructs. In F. M., & L. L. Putnam (Eds.), *The new handbook of organizational communication: Advances in theory, research, and methods*, (pp. 47-77). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- Cooke, R. A., & Lafferty, J. C. (2003). *Level V: Organizational culture inventory form III*. Plymouth, MI: Human Synergistics.

- Cooke, R. A., & Rousseau, D. M. (1988). Behavioral norms and expectations: a quantitative approach to the assessment of organizational culture. *Group & Organization Studies*, *13*, 245-73.
- Cooke, R. A., & Szumal, J. L. (1993). Measuring normative beliefs and shared behavioral expectations in organizations: the reliability and validity of the organizational culture inventory. *Psychological Reports*, *72*, 1299-1330.
- Cooke, R. A., & Szumal, J. L. (2000). Using the organizational culture inventory to understand the operating cultures of organizations. In N. M., Ashkanasy, C. P. M., Wilderom, & M. F. Peterson (Eds.), *Handbook of organizational culture and climate* (pp. 147-162). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications, Inc.
- de Cock, G., de Witte, K., & van Nieuwkerke, S. (1998). Effective communication within the organization. In P. J. D. Drenth, H. Thierry, & C. J. de Wolff (Eds.), *Handbook of work and organizational psychology: Organizational Psychology* (2nd ed., Vol. 4, pp. 387-400). Hove, UK: Psychology Press Ltd.
- Deal, T. E., & Kennedy, A. A. (1982). *Corporate cultures: The rites and rituals of organizational life*. Reading, MA: Addison Wesley.
- Dekker, S. W. A. (2007). *Just Culture: Balancing safety and accountability*. Aldershot, UK: Ashgate.
- Denison, D., Nieminen, L., & Kotrba, L. (2014). Diagnosing organizational cultures: A conceptual and empirical review of culture effectiveness surveys. *European Journal of Work and Organizational Psychology*, *23* (1), 145-161.
- Detert, J. R., Schroeder, R. G., & Mauriel, J. J. (2000). A framework for linking culture and improvement initiatives in organizations. *Academy of Management Review*, *25*, 850–863.

- Erez, M., & Gati, E. (2004). A dynamic, multi-level model of culture: from the micro level of the individual to the macro level of a global culture. *Applied Psychology, 53* (4), 583-598.
- Fischer, R., Ferreira, M. C., Assmar, E. M. L., Redford, P., & Harb, C. (2005). Organizational behaviour across cultures theoretical and methodological issues for developing multi-level frameworks involving culture. *International Journal of Cross Cultural Management, 5* (1), 27-48.
- García-Herrero, S., Mariscal, M. A., Gutiérrez, J. M., & Toca-Otero, A. (2013). Bayesian network analysis of safety culture and organizational culture in a nuclear power plant. *Safety science, 53*, 82-95.
- Glendon, A. I., & Stanton, N. A. (2000). Perspectives on safety culture. *Safety Science, 34* (1), 193-214.
- Guldenmund, F. W. (2000). The nature of safety culture: a review of theory and research. *Safety science, 34* (1), 215-257.
- Guldenmund, F. W. (2010). (Mis) understanding safety culture and its relationship to safety management. *Risk analysis, 30* (10), 1466-1480.
- Haley, B. R. (1998). *The relationship of unit culture and RN and client outcomes*. Unpublished doctoral dissertation, University of Illinois, Chicago.
- Health and Safety Executive (HSE) (2011). *High reliability organizations. A review of the literature* (N° 899 Research Report). London, UK: Crown.
- Huberty, C. J., & Petoskey, M. D. (2000). Multivariate analysis of variance and covariance. In H. Tinsley and S. Brown (Eds.) *Handbook of applied multivariate statistics and mathematical modeling*. New York: Academic Press.
- Institute of Nuclear Power Operations (INPO) (2013). *Traits of a nuclear safety culture*. Atlanta, GA: INPO.

- Johns, G. (2006). The essential impact of context on organizational behavior. *Academy of management review*, 31 (2), 386-408.
- Klein, R. L., Bigley, G. A., & Roberts, K. H. (1995). Organizational culture in high reliability organizations: An extension. *Human Relations*, 48 (7), 771-793.
- Kline, R. B. (2005). *Principles and practice of structural equation modeling* (2nd ed.). New York, NY: Guilford Press.
- Kwantes, C. T., & Boglarsky, C. A. (2004). Do occupational groups vary in expressed organizational culture preferences? A study of six occupations in the United States. *International Journal of Cross Cultural Management*, 4 (3), 335-354.
- Langan-Fox, J. (2001). Communication in organizations: Speed, diversity, networks, and influence on organizational effectiveness, human health, and relationships. In N. Anderson, D. S. Ones, H. K. Sinangil, & C. Viswesvaran (Eds.), *Handbook of industrial, Work & Organizational psychology* (pp. 188-205). London, UK: Sage.
- Maslow, A. H. (1954). *Motivation and personality*. New York, NY: Harper.
- Morrow, S. L., Koves, G. K., & Barnes, V. E. (2014). Exploring the relationship between safety culture and safety performance in US nuclear power operations. *Safety Science*, 69, 37-47.
- Mueller, R. O., & Hancock, G. Y. R. (2008). Best practices in structural equation modeling. In J. Osborne (Ed.), *Best practices in quantitative methods* (pp. 488-508). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- Murphy, P. J., Cooke, R. A., & Lopez, Y. (2013). Firm culture and performance: intensity's effects and limits. *Management Decision*, 51 (3), 661-679.
- Muthén, L.K., & Muthén, B.O., (1998-2012). Mplus User's Guide. Sixth Edition. Los Angeles, CA: Muthén & Muthén.

- Nagy, M. S. (2002). Using a single-item approach to measure facet job satisfaction. *Journal of Occupational and Organizational Psychology*, 75 (1), 77-86.
- Navajas, J., Silla, I., & Guldenmund, F. (2014). *Problem identification in high reliability organizations. An exploratory study in the nuclear Spanish sector*. Presented at the 7th International Conference of WOS.net, Glasgow, UK.
- Nuclear Regulatory Commission (NRC) (2005). *Guidance for Establishing and Maintaining a Safety Conscious Work Environment* (N° 2005-18). Washington D. C.: NRC Regulatory Issue Summary.
- Nuclear Energy Institute (NEI) (2003). *Nuclear power plant personnel-employee concerns program-process tools in a safety conscious work environment*. Washington D.C.: Nuclear Energy Institute.
- Nuclear Regulatory Commission (NRC) (2011). *Safety-conscious work environment issue of concern follow up* (Inspection procedure 93100). Washington D. C.: NRC inspection manual.
- Ostroff, C., Kinicki, A. J., & Tamkins, M. M. (2003). Organizational culture and climate. In W. C. Borman, D. R. Ilgen, & R. J. Kimoski (Eds.), *Handbook of psychology, Vol 12*, (pp. 565–593). New York, NY: John Wiley & Sons, Inc.
- Perin, C. (2005). *Shouldering risks: the culture of control in the nuclear power industry*. Princeton, NJ: Princeton University Press.
- Perrow, C. (1984). *Normal accidents*. New York, NY: Basic Books.
- Pidgeon, N. F. (1991). Safety culture and risk management in organizations. *Journal of Cross-Cultural Psychology*, 22 (1), 129-140.
- Pidgeon, N. F. (1997). The limits to safety: culture, politics, learning and man-made disasters?. *Journal of Contingencies and Crisis Management*, 5 (1), 1-14.

- Pool, S. W. (2000). Organizational culture and its relationship between job tension in measuring outcomes among business executives. *The Journal of Management Development*, 19 (1), 32-48.
- Reason, J. T. (1997). *Managing the risks of organizational accidents*. Aldershot, UK: Ashgate.
- Roberts, K. H. (1990). Some characteristics of one type of high reliability organization. *Organization Science*, 1 (2), 160-176.
- Roberts, K. H., & Bea, R. (2001). Must accidents happen? Lessons from high-reliability organisations. *Academy of Management Executive*, 15 (3), 70-79.
- Roberts, K. H., Rousseau, D. M., & La Porte, T. R. (1994). The culture of high reliability: Quantitative and qualitative assessment aboard nuclear-powered aircraft carriers. *The Journal of High Technology Management Research*, 5 (1), 141-161.
- Rousseau, D. M. (1989). The price of success? Security-oriented cultures and high reliability organizations. *Industrial Crisis Quarterly*, 3 (4), 285-302.
- Sackmann, S. A. (2011). Culture and performance. In N. Ashkanasy, C. Wilderom, & M. Peterson (Eds.), *The handbook of organizational culture and climate* (2nd ed., pp. 188-224). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- Sagan, S. D. (1993). *The limits of safety*. Princeton, NJ: Princeton University Press.
- Schall, M. S. (1983). A Communication-Rules Approach to Organizational Culture. *Administrative Science Quarterly*, 28 (4), 557-581.
- Smircich, L. (1983). Concepts of culture and organizational analysis. *Administrative science quarterly*, 28, 339-358.

- Stebbins, L. H. (2008). *An investigation of individual job satisfaction as an outcome of individual perception of organizational culture*. Unpublished doctoral dissertation, TUI University, College of business administration, California.
- Stohl, C. (1995). *Organizational Communication. Connectedness in action*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications.
- Szumal, J. L. (2009). *Organizational Culture Inventory. Interpretation and development guide*. Plymouth, MI: Human Synergistics.
- Tabachnick, B. G., & Fidell, L. S. (2007). *Using multivariate statistics*. Boston: Pearson/Allyn & Bacon.
- Tamuz, M., & Harrison, M. I. (2006). Improving patient safety in hospitals: contributions of high-reliability theory and normal accident theory. *Health services research, 41* (4), 1654-1676.
- Turner, B.A., & Pidgeon, N.F. (1997). *Man-made Disasters* (2nd ed.). Oxford, UK: Elsevier.
- Vaughan, D. (2009). *The Challenger launch decision: Risky technology, culture, and deviance at NASA*. Chicago, IL: University of Chicago Press.
- Vogus, T. J., & Welbourne, T. M. (2003). Structuring for high reliability: HR practices and mindful processes in reliability-seeking organizations. *Journal of Organizational Behavior, 24* (7), 877-903.
- Waller, M. J., & Roberts, K. H. (2003). High reliability and organizational behavior: finally the twain must meet. *Journal of Organizational Behavior, 24*, 813-814.
- Wanous, J. P., Reichers, A. E., & Hudy, M. J. (1997). Overall job satisfaction: How good are single-item measures?. *Journal of Applied Psychology, 82*, 247–252.

- Weick, K. E., & Sutcliffe, K. M. (2007). *Managing the unexpected. Resilient performance in the age of uncertainty* (2nd ed.). San Francisco, CA: Jossey-Bass.
- Xenikou, A., & Furnham, A. (1996). A correlational and factor analytic study of four questionnaire measures of organizational culture. *Human Relations*, 49 (3), 349-371.
- Xie, S., Helfert, M., Lugmayr, A., Heimgärtner, R., & Holzinger, A. (2013). Influence of Organizational Culture and Communication on the Successful Implementation of Information Technology in Hospitals. *Cross-Cultural Design. Cultural Differences in Everyday Life* (pp. 165-174). Las Vegas, NV: Springer Berlin Heidelberg, Lecture Notes in Computer Science.

Acknowledgements

The Spanish Electricity Industry Association (UNESA) provided financial support to conduct this study.